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18

**COMPARISON OF INTRACUFF AIR SALINE 2 percent LIGNOCAINE
ALKALIZED LIGNOCAINE 2 percent TO PREVENT SORE THROAT IN
PATIENTS WITH GENERAL ANAESTHESIA BY ENDOTRACHEAL
INTUBATION**

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ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND: Postoperative Sore throat and cough during emergence are common side effects of general anaesthesia and its incidence is reported by 30-80% of patients after tracheal intubation. Also, not to forget the hemodynamic fluctuations associated with it, adds on to the magnitude of the problem. Thinking of a simple and cost-effective way to tackle this problem, this study was undertaken to determine the benefits of using intra-cuff lignocaine, alkalized lignocaine to prevent post intubation sore throat and emergence cough. **AIMS & OBJECTIVE:** The objective of this study was to assess the efficacy of intra-cuff 2% lignocaine solution, intracuffed alkalized lignocaine 2% in reducing emergence cough and post-operative sore throat after extubation in general surgery patients intubated for 2-4 hours.

METHODS: In a comparative observational study done in tertiary care hospital, where 200 ASA I and II status patients divided into 4 groups of 50 each were compared for Sore throat, throat pain, cough & restlessness. In group A, ETT cuff was filled with air, in group B with Normal saline, in group C 2% plain lignocaine solution, in group D Alkalinised 2% lignocaine 9 cc 2% lignocaine with 1cc sodabicarb 8.5%w/w was used. Side effects like sore throat, coughing and restlessness were assessed. Chi square and ANOVA test were used to compare the findings.

RESULTS: Postoperative sore throat (POST), cough, restlessness, throat pain are least with Alkalinised Lignocaine, & then in decreasing order with Lignocaine, saline & air groups.

CONCLUSIONS: This study proves that 2% intra-cuff alkalized lignocaine is an effective method in reducing post-operative sore throat and emergence cough.

KEYWORDS: Intra-cuff air, Intracuff alkalised 2% lignocaine, Lignocaine 2%, saline, POST (Post-Operative Sore Throat).

INTRODUCTION

Endotracheal intubation is gold standard form of airway intervention and ventilation management for major surgical procedures under general anaesthesia.

After intubation, inflating a cuff around the endotracheal tube maintains a seal, but at the same time, stimulates the irritant receptors in the trachea resulting in coughing during emergence from anaesthesia. Coughing is hazardous overall & especially in neurosurgical, ophthalmic, and vascular procedures. The incidence of coughing on emergence from general anaesthesia in the presence of an endotracheal tube has been estimated between 38% and 96%. (1) The patient when unable to tolerate an endo-tracheal tube coughs on the tube and this is also called bucking. Mucosal erosion may also be caused by mucosal dehydration and the patient bucking or coughing causing friction between the tracheal mucosa and the endotracheal tube, leading to post-operative sore throat. The overall incidence of sore throat after general anaesthesia is between 59-76% in 2002. (2)

administration of IV or topically applied local anaesthetics, IV narcotic administration and tracheal extubation in a deep plane of anaesthesia; however, in many cases they are undesirable. (3-7) The benefit of topically applied drugs before tracheal intubation is limited to a short time post application, as they are absorbed through the tracheo-bronchial mucosa. (8)

The cuff could act as a potential reservoir for a local anaesthetic, allowing diffusion and subsequent anaesthesia of the underlying mucosa. In this technique, plasma levels of lignocaine rise much slowly than in cases of direct topical application, thus reducing the risk of toxicity. Topical anaesthetics applied in this manner might represent a novel technique to reduce adverse emergence coughing and post-operative sore throat

METHODS

After taking Informed consent of patient this study was carried out in 200 patients for various surgeries conducted under General Anaesthesia with endotracheal intubation for 200 adult patients of ASA grade 1/2. Preoperative detail assessment was done & VAS was explained to each patient so that Postoperatively VAS was accessed easily.

Inclusion Criteria

Adult patients of ASA grade 1/2 having age of 18-60 yrs. with Normal BMI having surgical duration of 2 hrs. at least.

Exclusion criteria

They were allergy to lignocaine, patients with cardio respiratory diseases, obesity, difficulty in intubation and risk of aspiration, Smokers, those undergoing airway, head and neck surgeries and those with a previous history of airway surgery.

At the time of Anaesthesia patients were randomized with Randomization table, & divided in groups A, B, C, D.

After taking informed consent, & confirming 6 hrs. nil by mouth patients were anaesthetized with inj. Glycopyrrolate 0.04 mg/kg, injection midazolam 0.02 mg/kg, injection Fentanyl 1 mcg/kg, as premedication, whereas injection Thiopentone 5-6 mg/kg & inj. suxamethonium 2 mg/kg, Endotracheal intubation was done with appropriate size tube (For female 7.5 no, for male 8.5 no ETT). After proper fixation Endotracheal cuff was filled with minimum volume of filling agent to prevent leak according to Randomized group allocation. Randomization was done by Randomization table software available on internet. In group A, ETT cuff was filled with air, in group B with Normal saline, in group C 2% plain lignocaine solution, in group D Alkalinised 2% lignocaine (9 cc 2% lignocaine with 1cc sodabcarb 8.4% w/w prepared in this manner and) effective volume taken from it) was used. Maintenance of Anaesthesia was done by O₂, N₂O & Sevoflurane 2-3% with inj. Atracurium 0.5 mg/kg as bolus dose & as when required according to neuromuscular monitoring.

At the patient end Heat moisture exchanger HME was attached & then patients were managed on Drager Fabius GS workstation with volume control ventilation.

At end of surgery patients were reversed with injection glycopyrrolate & neostigmine. Extubation was done after fulfillment of extubation criteria, spontaneous respiration & sustained head lift for at least 20 secs, response to verbal commands & adequate motor tone & power. patients were watched in postoperative ward for VAS (0-100mm) for throat pain (13), Adverse effects like sore throat, coughing and blood pressure were assessed postoperatively after extubation 1 hr, 2 hr, 12 hr, 24 hr. Postoperatively injection paracetamol 1 gr. was given for analgesia to alleviate visceral pain of surgery in each patient.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

Observations were taken & noted on spreadsheet. For statistical analysis IBM software Armonk NY 2016 was used. ANOVA test for numerical variables and Chi square test for categorical variables were used to compare the findings among groups.

RESULTS:**Table 1 Demographic parameters**

Patients Parameters	Gr A (n=50)	Gr B (n=50)	Gr C (n=50)	Gr. D (n=50)	P value
Age (yrs.)	42+/-8	40+/-6	41+/-7	43+/-5	>0.05
Weight(kg)	51+/-6	50+/-7	55+/-4	52+/-5	>0.05
ASA grade(I/Ii)	25/25	24/26	26/24	27/23	>0.05
BMI (number)	22+/-4	21+/-5	20+/-4	23+/-3	>0.05
Mean Duration of surgery(min)	118+/-13	110+/-15	113+/-12	121-/-10	>0.05

Table 2 Intraoperative Haemodynamic parameters

Haemodynamic Parameters	Gr A (n=50)	Gr B (n=50)	Gr C (n=50)	Gr D (n=50)	P value
Mean HR	68+/-5	70+/-4	66+/-6	63+/-6	>0.05
Mean SBP	110+/-8	118+/-5	116+/-8	112+/-6	>0.05
Mean MAP	76+/-8	78+/-6	80+/-4	82+/-6	>0.05

All patients in each group have stable haemodynamic parameters

Table 3: VAS scale for throat pain

VAS	GrA	Gr B	Gr C	Gr D	P value
At 1 hr.	6.2+/-0.5	5.5+/-0.2	4.8+/-0.4	4.2+/-0.3	<9.05
At 2 hr.	5.8+/-0.2	5.3+/-0.3	4.5+/-0.2	4.0+/-0.2	<9.05
At 6 hr.	4.4+/-0.4	4.8+/-0.4	4.2+/-0.3	3.8+/-0.4	<9.05
At 12hr	4.2+/-0.2	4.0+/-0.2	3.8+/-0.3	3.5+/-0.4	<9.05
At 24 hr.	3.6+/-0.4	3.5+/-0.4	3.3+/-0.2	3.1+/-0.2	<9.05

There was a gradual decrease in the pain score in all groups periodically over 24 hours. Over all the pain score was less in the group D, in decreasing followed order by the group C, B & A.

Table 4 Comparison of Intracuff volume at different times

Time at which volume measured	Gr A	Gr B	Gr C	Gr D	P value
Volume At time of inflation(ml)	4+/-0.2	3.8+/-0.8	4.1+/-0.2	4.0+/-0.3	>0.05

Volume At time of deflation(ml)	6+/-0.4	4.5+/-0.4	3.8+/-0.4	3.6+/-0.6	<0.05
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Table 4 shows that volume at inflation was comparable ($P>0.05$) whereas at time of deflation volume was increase in Gr A, whereas it was almost same in other groups.

Comparison of Incidence of Restlessness

At time of extubation 88, %&80% of patients experienced restlessness in the A& B group respectively, while it was 80% and 56.7% in C and D groups respectively. ($p>0.05$).

At 1 hr., restlessness was seen in 49%in group A,43.3% in the group B, 20% in C group and 13.3% in the group, D with a statistically significant difference ($p<0.05$) among groups.

At 2 hr., there was 6.7% incidence of restlessness in the group D, which was lowest incidence than any other groups.

There was no statistically significant difference between the groups at 12&24 hours. ($P>0.05$)

Comparison of Incidence of cough

During extubation incidence of cough was highest in the group A (96.7%) followed by group B (90%), then group C (80%) and group D (66.7%). There was statistically significant difference among the groups which was measured by chi square test. ($p<0.05$) At 1 hour 72.2% in group A,63.3% of patients had cough in the group B while in the group C it was 30% and 26.7% in the group D. ($P<0.05$)

At 2 hr. in all groups incidence of cough was lesser then 1st hr. of extubation

At 12 hrs. no patient in group D has coughing, in group C9% of patients had it, in group B it was of 12%, In Group A it was 15% ($P<0.05$)

At 24 hrs. no patient in group D had cough whereas 3%in group C,5% in group B, & group A it was of 7%. ($p<0.05$)

Comparison of incidence of sore throat

At 1 hr. of extubation 88% in group A,75%in group B,60% in group C, & 25%of group D patients have sore throat.

At 2 hrs. of extubation 84% in A group,72% in B group,55% in C group, & 20% in D group had sore throat. ($p<0.001$)

At 12 hours, 77% in A group,66.7% of patients had a sore throat in the B group, 50 % in the C group and 16.7% in the D group patients had sore throat. ($P<0.001$)

At 24 hours, 33.3% of patients had sore throat in B group, 20% in the C group and no incidence in the D group. There was a statistically significant difference among the groups ($p<0.001$)

Haemodynamic parameters of all group's patients were stable & comparable after extubation ($p>0.05$)

DISCUSSION

Postoperative sore throat occurs in 80- 90% of intubated patients and is the most common complaint after tracheal intubation & various agents like air, saline, Intracuff Lignocaine, Lignocaine topical 10% are used for prevention .(10-14) The insertion of tracheal tube can damage the upper respiratory mucosa resulting in a hematoma, laceration or granuloma of the mucosa, or arytenoids cartilage damage.(15) The ETT may also damage the anterior branch of the recurrent laryngeal nerve causing cord paralysis and external laryngeal nerve damage causing cricothyroid muscle paralysis.(16)These factors may result in hoarseness. Sore throat is due to various factors like endotracheal tube size, design, lateral wall pressure, intracuff pressure, use of cleansing agents, lubricants, hypotension, local infection, use of steroids, and the duration of intubation. It has been proposed that the incidence and severity of sore throat after intubation is highly co-related to endotracheal cuff design and was explained on the basis of cuff-trachea contact area. As per the study conducted by Singh Hemit et al (17)

in adult patients of ASA 1 or 2 using intracuff alkaline lignocaine, plain lignocaine and air as control, concluded that incidence of post-operative sore throat and other indirect effects to tracheal extubation such as haemodynamic changes, restlessness, dysphonia and hoarseness was less during the post op period. The use of intracuff lignocaine increased tolerance to tubing in the trachea and allowed a smooth emergence. same as our study. Acharya et al (18) in their study comparing alkaline lignocaine and air, concluded that addition of alkalinized lignocaine maintained a stable cuff pressure during oxygen and nitrous oxide anaesthesia this prevented the damage that occurred due to increased cuff pressure during general anaesthesia

Manimala et al (19) conducted a study in two groups with plain lignocaine 4% instillation and air in cuff concluded significantly reduced the post intubation co-morbidity as compared to air and hence it should be routinely practiced in all intubated patients. Though results appear to be similar to my study they did not advocate the use of alkaline lignocaine.

Souissi et al (20) in their study in 2016 including 80 participants of a tertiary care center who received intracuff alkalinized lidocaine or intracuff 0.9% saline showed that the use of 160 mg of intracuff alkalinized lignocaine is associated with N2O used General Anaesthesia a decreased incidence of cough upon emergence & showed that Alkalisied lignocaine will produce the desired action after optimal duration for absorption.

Lam F, Lin Y-C et al (21) in their systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized control trials evaluating intracuff alkaline lignocaine in endotracheal tube concluded the effectiveness of intracuff lignocaine used in the prevention of emergence phenomenon.

Navarro LH, Lima RM et al (22) in their study evaluated 50 smoking patients comparing intracuff alkaline lignocaine and saline and demonstrated decreasing the incidence of emergence coughing and sore throat during the postoperative period in smokers. This study was conducted in a group with high airway reflexivity to chemical and mechanical stimulations.

Previous studies of Gaur p. et al (23) have showed increased cuff pressure and volume over time after air inflation, Increased the incidence of POST (23) During anaesthesia using nitrous oxide, the cuff pressure increases as the temperature of the cuff rises and nitrous oxide diffuses into it more rapidly than it leaves. This over inflation of the ETT has been associated with damage to pharyngeal mucosa and recurrent laryngeal nerve palsy. It would also cause increased receptor stimulation in the tracheal mucosa and thus increase emergence and extubation phenomena. The complications were decreased by filling the ETT cuff with liquid. In present study it was observed that the initial air volume required to inflate the cuff was significantly greater than the liquid volume. At the time of extubation air volume in the cuff increased owing to diffusion. In the group.

In our study, incidence of sore throat was least when intracuff alkalinized lignocaine was used rather than plain lignocaine, saline & air. Throat pain and restlessness were most common in the group A in which air was the inflating medium. Compared to plain lignocaine group & saline group, the incidence of side effects was less in the alkalinized lignocaine group.

CONCLUSION

In nutshell, Intracuffed Alkaline Lignocaine is most promising agent to prevent sore throat It reduces, incidence of throat pain, cough, & restlessness after general anaesthesia with endotracheal intubation then other agents

LIMITATIONS OF STUDY:

1. We could not measure Intracuff pressure because of unavailability of Intracuff pressure monitor
2. Inj. Paracetamol 1gm. was used to prevent visceral pain of surgery which may effect on VAS for throat pain.

FUTURE RECOMMENDATIONS: We recommend not to use air as Intracuff sealing agent of endotracheal tube to prevent postoperative sore throat (POST)

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